

Consciousness of Tolerance in the Context of Eastern-Western Cultures

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Abstract

The author of the article CONSCIOUSNESS OF TOLERANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF EASTERN-WESTERN CULTURES analyzed in his research that the East and the West have developed in mutual relations throughout history, and at the same time, the existence of various contradictions in the relations between them, and evaluated the similar and different characteristics of the tolerant mindset of the individual based on scientific sources. Scientific-objective and logical research suggests that the processes taking place in the modern Globalization phase and the development of tolerant mindset will further strengthen the relations between Eastern and Western civilizations and regulate conflicts.

Keywords: philosophy, culture, enlightenment, freedom, East, West

Introduction

Despite the extensive and consistent atheism education during the seventy-year existence of the Soviet-Russian empire, which included the Republic of Azerbaijan, it was not possible to raise a "godless generation" and people preserved religion in the depths of their consciousness. Today, every citizen living in Azerbaijan freely and freely belongs to the religion of their choice. The Constitution of Azerbaijan declares that a democratic, legal, secular and unitary Republic has been established, and religion is separated from the state. In the independent Azerbaijani state, the education system is secular in nature, citizens practice the traditions of the religion of their choice, the state does not interfere unduly in the work of believers and religious organizations, but on the contrary, creates conditions for their normal activity. As an example, we can cite the fact that after independence in Azerbaijan, the activity of old mosques, churches and synagogues has been strengthened, even new ones have been built and put into operation, and the activities of religious educational institutions have expanded.

It is no coincidence that the National Leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev, who highly appreciated the State-Nation principle as a principle of political governance, always treated the national-spiritual values of the people, including their religion, with great respect and reverence. A worthy successor to Heydar Aliyev's policy, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev said: "The high humanity inherent in the Azerbaijani people, the atmosphere of national-religious tolerance prevailing in our society, socio-political stability and civil solidarity, mutual respect and trust between ethnic minorities and religious communities have made our country an example of tolerance in the world. We are rightly proud of this. Ensuring the rights and freedoms of every Azerbaijani citizen,

regardless of their language, religion, or ethnic affiliation, will always be the focus of the state's attention"¹.

1. 1 Specific features of Eastern-Western cultures and tolerance

The realities of the modern era create favorable conditions for a fundamentally new perception of the mutual relations of culture and personality. The point is that the entire life world surrounding a person unconditionally acquires cultural-creative significance. Culture is increasingly gaining meaning in all the diverse forms of manifestation of human existence. A person acts as a "cultured person" regardless of his specifically understood level of cultural development. At present, the individual's attitude to culture is also completely different from traditional forms. It is known that a person's presence in culture is not always perceived at a conscious level in the true sense of the word, but it always means experiencing and feeling a person's natural belonging to the cultural world. Therefore, the attitude of every believer, individual to culture expresses the practical task of preserving and strengthening cultural traditions, language, customs, and all the factors that make up the cultural environment as a whole. When approached from this point of view, the presence of a person in the world of culture acts as his real life process. Modern Azerbaijani society is a social system in which certain problems are manifested in the life activity of the personality, its tolerance, its self-determination and value orientation. This once again proves that a deep social and philosophical analysis of the problem of modern personality can play an important role in developing the right program of action both on the scale of society as a whole and at the level of an individual taken separately, in the effective formation of value-motivational guidelines.

Today, Azerbaijan is a country where a unique model of secular power and state-religion relations emerged from the constructive activity and mutual communication of religious communities, which can serve as an example even for the most democratic states on earth. As the head of the Georgian Orthodox Church, Catholicos Ilya II, who visited Azerbaijan, said, "Azerbaijan is a country that not only exports oil to the world, but also exports tolerance"².

1.2 A culture of tolerance with very ancient historical roots and rich traditions in Azerbaijan

Tolerance, which benefits from Islamic values and is based on mutual respect, beneficial communication and unshakable cooperation, has very ancient historical roots and rich traditions in Azerbaijan. Because during the history of our statehood, anti-Semitism has never manifested itself in Azerbaijan, and members of various sects and religions, who were subjected to severe pressure and persecution in various countries, were confident in the tolerance and high humanity of our people, and therefore took refuge in our homeland with great confidence and considered our country a place of hope for themselves. Islam not only did not prohibit religions that preceded it, but on the contrary, it created conditions for treating all religions with respect, patience, care and dignity, and for the freedom of conscience of people who believe in different religions, and for the inviolability of the right to freely perform their religious rites and ceremonies. It is for this reason that various peoples who have settled in Azerbaijan for many centuries have been able to preserve their religious beliefs to this day. It can be said with certainty that a model of Islamic religion specific to our country has already emerged in Azerbaijan. The changes that have taken place in the socio-

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political, as well as scientific and cultural life in different periods of our country's development have led to the implementation of a pro-Western policy by Eastern Azerbaijan and its rapid integration into the world. The Azerbaijani people have preserved a large part of their customs and traditions that have been passed down for centuries within the framework of the Islamic religion, and a number of Islamic values have become the spiritual qualities of the people and the main features of their mentality. Today, Islam in Azerbaijan does not hinder development, but on the contrary, it is considered a factor that purifies it, protects it from elements that can harm national and spiritual values, and gives it internal strength.

The founder of the modern Azerbaijani state, Heydar Aliyev, has repeatedly stated that all religions, regardless of their nationality, rooted in love, loyalty and faith in God, have throughout history instilled in people purity, cleanliness, patriotism and humanity, and have been guarantors of truth and justice in human relations. The great leader Heydar Aliyev used to say: "We are walking on the straight path, on the path of truth, on the path of God, on the path of truth, on the path of independence". The fact that our country took its rightful place among the members of the Organization of the Islamic Conference, increased attention to religious institutions and religious educational institutions in Azerbaijan, and the great leader's signing of a decree on the establishment of the State Committee for Work with Religious Institutions in 2001 were a vivid example of his respect and reverence for religion. A whole historical stage of Azerbaijan, a multinational and multi-confessional state, is associated with his name, with progressive traditions, the creation of an environment of ethnic and religious tolerance in the country, which is the basis of socio-political stability and national-spiritual solidarity. To date, 336 Islamic and 31 non-Islamic religious communities have been registered with the State Committee for Work with Religious Organizations. Of the latter, 20 represent Christianity, 7 represent Judaism, 3 represent Baha'ism, and 1 represents Krishnaism. Today, the unhindered activity of about 40 Russian Orthodox, Albanian-Udin churches, Jewish synagogues, Christian-Malakan and Christian-Baptist communities, and many religious educational institutions affiliated with them in our republic is a clear evidence of the day-by-day strengthening of the atmosphere of tolerance and the expansion of interfaith dialogue in Azerbaijan, a secular state.

2. Tolerance and Identity

When analyzing the modern personality in the context of culture, the growing role of dialogue in its communication system should be especially noted. In this regard, the expanding processes of democratization, the creation of real conditions for pluralism of ideas and tolerance are of exceptional importance. By the way, let us note that the increase in the role of dialogue and communicability as an important feature characterizing the personality is a general global process that is not limited to the borders of one or another country. This is explained, first of all, by the increase in the indicators of social development of man at the modern stage of civilization, the extraordinary expansion of his general cultural level and creative horizons. It is no coincidence that hermeneutics, one of the most influential philosophical teachings of the modern era, considers the problems of human dialogicity and communicability to be among its central themes. Representatives of this teaching study dialogue on a wide scale and approach it as a creative form of personality, a method of human self-development and expansion of his social world. What has been said shows that dialogue occupies an important and unique place in the cultural system of modern society. The process of transformation of the general cultural environment of modern society and the attitude of the personality to other subjects in conditions of tolerance are also of great importance. Thus, new cultural patterns reflecting the general state of society and the prospects for its development arise precisely in the sphere of intersubjective interaction. The

said interaction can be carried out mainly in two forms (dialogue and monologue). Accordingly, the socially oriented cultural activity of the personality takes place.

When examining the level of tolerant consciousness of the personality type of the modern era from the position of culture, the following point must be taken into account. We are talking about the need to approach this problem in a dynamic situation, to consider it in connection with real processes. The essence of the issue is that the fundamental changes taking place in all spheres and aspects of social life now find their corresponding reflection in the tolerance and culture of the personality of this era. The mutual relations of these factors are dynamic in nature. It is rich in content and combines the spontaneous and spontaneous, natural interaction between the human personality and culture, the interaction between them, which is formed by forms of public consciousness (science, art, morality, philosophy), mass consciousness and public psychology, and is expressed in the transforming spiritual and material activity, which is conditioned by the consciousness of man, his psyche, and his active, creative nature. Despite the fact that the modern personality has all its colorful cultural qualities, it mainly operates in the orbit of two cultural centers (West and East). The East and the West have developed and risen in interaction with each other throughout history, but at the same time, various difficulties and contradictions have also manifested themselves in their relations. The issue of relations between East and West civilizations, which has been going on for centuries, is being discussed more often today. Debates about the future of the two regions in question, whether a single world community can be created through the organic connection of their achievements and advantages, do not subside. Naturally, in this case, the conversation also raises the issue of the personality's attitude to the cultural and spiritual achievements of the East and the West. Taken as a whole, the essence of the issue is to clearly identify the common and unique aspects of the historical traditions and cultures of Eastern and Western civilizations and to investigate the possibilities, forms and ways for the modern personality to integrate them into itself.

2.1 The problem of personality in the context of the East and the West

First of all, let us note that the analysis of the problem of personality in the context of the East and the West is not taken in a geographical sense, but in a philosophical-sociological sense. In other words, when we say "West", we mean the European way of life, style of thinking, rationalism, Christian religious traditions, experience gained in the field of democracy and the rule of law, giving priority to the individual, personality in relation to the collective, the successes of scientific and technical development, and other issues. The philosophical meaning of the word "East" covers intuitionism, spirituality, the traditions of Eastern religions, especially Islam, the priority of the second party in the individual-collective system, etc.

The outstanding philosopher of the 20th century A. Schweitzer showed that there is one great problem that interests every philosophy. This is the problem of how to achieve unity of man with infinite being. Approaching the relations of Western-Eastern philosophical thought from that prism, he noted that they act as opposite poles to each other. The main difference between them is that the West tries to solve the above-mentioned problem mainly by strengthening faith in the world and human life, while the East tries to solve it by denying the world and life as a whole. In this regard, it should be noted that setting the East against the West is not a new issue, it has an ancient history. Thus, some representatives of ancient philosophy spoke from this position. Since the early Middle Ages, the concept of the East in the lexicon of the West began to be taken more broadly in terms of content. Along with the traditionally taken India, China and Iran, newly formed Muslim countries were also added to this. This was not accidental, but was due to a number of reasons. First of all, the powerful

and large-scale invasions of the leaders of Muslim countries that took place one after another starting from that period (especially the military campaigns of the Caliphate in the 7th-9th centuries, and later the Ottomans) shook Europe and forced them to approach the Eastern factor more seriously in a military-political plan. Another reason, in our opinion, has a religious meaning. The point is that the emergence of a new monotheistic religion, Islam, and its rapid spread over a short period of time deeply worried the Christian world. As a result of all this, the population of Western countries began to look down on the East. They portrayed themselves as the source of civilization and culture, and the East as a region at the level of barbarism. As a result, they formed the idea of approaching the East as something alien, a foreign culture. In return, the mood and way of thinking of the East also established the idea that the Christian world was instilling in people an alien culture and art, corrupt character and behavior, and immorality. Later, this polarization deepened. Accusations intensified in the public consciousness of the Eastern population that the Western world was chasing only material means of living and forgetting spirituality, ignoring personal freedom, and being addicted to pluralism. As a result, a specific Orientalism emerged - a tendency to exaggerate the historical and cultural achievements of the East as a sign of protest against various types of Eurocentric sentiment.

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2.3. Factors for the normalization of East-West relations

It should be noted that in the general historical process, separate serious conflict factors on secular and religious grounds have created a more favorable environment for conflicts on the basis of East-West relations and have strengthened them.

In this regard, the terrorist act that occurred on September 11, 2001 in two major cities of the United States (New York and Washington) and resulted in the death of thousands of people played a more serious role. True, statements were repeatedly made in official circles and at the level of heads of state that this was a terrorist act and had nothing to do with East-West, Islamic-Christian religious relations. Such ideas were voiced at various international meetings and scientific-theoretical conferences held thereafter, and it was shown that terrorists have no homeland and religion. Therefore, all countries of the world community must fight against terrorism and extremism, which have already taken on a global character, and create a single bloc. There is no doubt that these or other measures have played a significant role in the normalization of East-West relations. However, these relations are still far from the necessary level, there are often ideas and calls about the contradictions of the East-West regions, about their inability to reconcile and unite. It is no coincidence that representatives of Eurocentrism show that the culture of all peoples of the Earth is secondary, only the culture of the European people is the main one. L.N. Gumilyov expressed this tendency as follows: "The secret desire of every European is to destroy the unique cultural image of all peoples of the Earth, to see only European culture as a universal culture, and to turn all other cultures into a lower type of culture"⁴.

When analyzing Western and Eastern cultures in terms of their influence on the development of a tolerant consciousness of the individual, one cannot limit oneself to showing their similarities and differences in past historical stages. The main thing is not to forget the new qualities that the modern world has created in this regard. The point is that the 20th century has created a fundamentally new stage in the growth of the commonality and closeness of these two civilizations. The famous English historian A. Toynbee came to the conclusion that until the 20th century, humanity did not seem to have a common destiny. Different civilizations (Tibet, China, Egypt, pre-Columbian American civilization, etc.) often existed completely unaware of each other. Naturally, there was no question of a common historical experience between them. Now, however, the situation has changed radically, mass communication and information means between different continents have reached such a perfect level that it is possible to receive operational and accurate information about any event occurring in one place on the other side of the world.

3. Culture - Personality - Modernity

The great role of culture in the formation of the modern personality type is also expressed in the fact that as a result of the fundamental changes taking place in the present era, various and often contradictory moments in the spiritual world of man manifest themselves. In such conditions, man's searches for understanding the meaning of his existence are accelerated. The path of the latter mainly lies in the reinterpretation of spiritual values and appeal to cultural traditions. In this appeal, the personality tries to search for his

"I" in the modern transient world. In the process in question, the personality compares the cultural values of the modern West and the East with each other, justifies what he considers superior to them, and tries to implement them in his life activities by leaning towards them. The latter circumstance proves that now the personality sees the way out of the spiritual crisis he is facing also in the culture and civilization he considers progressive, where the factor of tolerance should be considered decisive.

In general, the cultural potential of the East is characterized by the strength of religion, the traditional organization of society, the strength of the socio-ethical style of the personality. The West, on the other hand, is characterized by the industrialization of society, the democratization of statehood, high technological development and its strong influence on public life. The strength of the latter factors often creates a state of technophobia in the personality in the West (a fear of technical development and, therefore, an attempt to turn away from it). Technophobia expresses a condition in which technical methods and objects are perceived by a person as a threat to his existence. In fact, this idea is also beginning to spread widely at the level of mass consciousness.

Even K. Jaspers substantiated the idea of the need to connect the progressive forms of Western and Eastern cultures with each other. He showed that universal "communications" should be created between cultures, religions and centuries. In other words, the philosopher characterized this as creating a philosophy of the "axial age", which instills the admonition of personal responsibility, which is the basis of Eastern and Western culture. "We seek unity at a higher level, at the level of the integrity of the world of human existence and creativity. In striving for this, we achieve the unity of previous eras by revealing the aspects that belong to all people, are important for all of them. However, the significance of this moment can only be revealed in the dynamics of human communication. By striving to create communication of unlimited scale, people are trying to embody the unification of their mutual relations around a single ideal axis that encompasses all of humanity"³.

3.1 Culture of the East and the West and the Principle of Dialogue

There are certain peculiarities in the culture of the East and the West, in the way of life and thinking of people, which are important to take into account. For example, in the East, the idea is that everything that exists is perfect from the day it was created, therefore all efforts should be aimed at preserving that perfection. Therefore, human creativity was almost not accepted and prohibited here. Then, the ecological problem in the East is also different from that in the West. In Eastern public opinion, such a position prevailed in relation to nature that nature was created as a perfect being, therefore it is necessary to preserve it as it is, not to interfere with it, not to spoil it. In Western public consciousness, for a long time, the "slogan" of not expecting mercy from nature, of subordinating it to ourselves, dominated. Then, the central principle of Western thinking and attitude to the world is activity, doing work, external activity. In the East, the central principle of thinking and attitude to the world is observation, reflection, and concentration of thought on the inner world.

Currently, various futurological concepts put forward ideas that modern industrially developed countries are moving towards a "post-industrial society". Here, along with the production of efficiently organized goods and services, the main attention is paid to the satisfaction of human needs in the true sense of the word. Examples of these needs include everyone's satisfaction with their work, protection of health in the labor process, implementation of forecasting at the international level, elimination of unjustified inequality manifested in society in various forms, etc. Among the ways to solve such issues and other

problems, a special place is occupied by the transition from the currently applied political-economic rationality to a new, cultural rationality in the future. It is suggested that precisely in conditions where cultural rationality will be established, a person will not be treated as a means to achieve a certain goal, but will be taken as the main goal in itself. It is also assumed that in the future, culture and civilization will become even closer to each other. Along with the changes in scientific-technical, technological fields and production, significant progress will also occur in people's behavior and morality, ethical and religious ideas. They, in turn, will create significant innovations in all areas of a person's life, in his attitude to his work, to his friends and those around him, in his tolerance.

In modern conditions, the main interests of humanity as a whole, as well as of each human personality, necessitate the expansion of dialogue between the West and the East. This need is now stronger than ever. At present, regardless of which region they live in, all people seem to be sailing on the same ship. Therefore, it is important to find and widely promote common and similar features inherent in these types of civilizations, rather than the features that separate and distinguish them, in the historical and national-cultural traditions of both the West and the East, and to follow the paths leading to mutual understanding and consent. In this regard, the following words of the great philosopher and public figure of the 20th century A. Schweitzer can be accepted as a principle: "Let us imagine that a dispute is taking place between European and Indian philosophy: each of them has the right to claim that it is exclusively correct. For both are temples of an extremely valuable treasury of ideas. Therefore, it is necessary for both the West and the East to rise above all historical differences that have existed between them in the past and to develop a single way of thinking for humanity." We see this idea clearly today in the example of independent Azerbaijan.

Discussion

Thus, the problem of West-Eastern relations in terms of their impact on the tolerance of the individual is quite complex and encompasses many directions and sides. When considering these issues, it is necessary to take into account, in addition to the aspects related to the specificity (mentality) of spiritual values and cultural wealth, which play an important role in the formation of individual qualities of the individual, their universal qualities as an inseparable unity. The history of the 20th century is marked by the development of relations between the countries of the world, the increase in their cooperation and unity, as well as the realization of historical responsibility in solving global problems of the era and issues of common destiny.

Conclusion

Our analysis based on the topic CONSCIOUSNESS OF TOLERANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF EASTERN-WESTERN CULTURES leads to the following main conclusions:

1. As in every historical stage, the development of personality and culture at the level of modern tolerant consciousness are inseparable, but the realities of the era in which we live are characterized by the further strengthening of their mutual relations. This is expressed in the fact that culture plays an increasingly important role in all forms of the personality's life activity, on the other hand, the personality is not limited to simply presenting existing cultural examples, but develops them creatively, thus having a significant impact on the rise of culture in society.
2. The created conditions and environment of tolerance, democratization, wide scope for ideological pluralism, free spiritual creativity, and the qualities of the modern personality

such as dialogicity and communicativeness further accelerate the process of forming a tolerant consciousness. At the same time, the dynamics characteristic of the modern level of interaction between personality and culture have a complex mechanism and are implemented in very different forms.

3. The political and cultural processes taking place in the modern world give reason to assume that tolerance, which is acquired by the common sense of humanity, will in the future eliminate the confrontation between Western and Eastern civilizations and further strengthen their mutual relations.
4. Strengthening a wide-scale dialogue between civilizations, linking the positive aspects of each of these cultures separately, and using them for the formation and development of personality are more specific for modern Azerbaijani society. Since our country is located on the border of the convergence of both civilizations in terms of geographical space, on the one hand, more favorable conditions are created here for linking the progressive aspects inherent in both cultures. On the other hand, since Azerbaijan is a unique meeting ground for both Western and Eastern cultural values, the requirement is put forward for each member of our society to be able to make the right choice in the labyrinth of spiritual values, which is of great importance in the enrichment of tolerant consciousness.
5. The wide presence of diversity of opinions and the dual assessment of objective realities in the assessment of relations between the East and the West, Islam and Christianity creates disagreements and contradictions on the basis of national-religious discrimination. In this case, tolerance does not eliminate differences of belief, but becomes one-sided. It must be mutual. In this regard, in modern conditions, there is a serious need for comprehensive scientific enlightenment to ensure that religious-political teachings and philosophical views do not lose their objectivity, and for interfaith dialogue and rapprochement.

Reference

- Heydər Əliyev. Müstəqillik yolu. Bakı, 1997
İmanov H., Əhədov A., Əhmədli N. Etnik dinlər və dünya dinləri. Bakı, Elm, 2003
Вебер М. Избранные произведения. М.: Прогресс, 1990
Гумилев Л.Н. Ритмы Евразии. М.: 1993
Франкл В. Человек в поисках смысла. М.: Республика, 1990
Фром Э. Психоанализ и этика. М., Наука, 1993
Швейцер А. Культура и этика. М.: 1979
Ясперс К. Смысл и назначение истории. М.: Республика, 1991